

The Academy of Business in Society

Highlights Report 2022

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Introduction

Dr. Ivo Matser EMP
Chief Executive Officer

Prof. Dr. Baback Yazdani
Chair of the Board of
Directors

Dear ABIS Partners and Members,

2022 was an eventful and challenging year. It seems that uncertain times are not over and over the last months, they have rather become even more turbulent and expose many challenges, dilemmas and conflicting solutions. This means that we need each other to better understand our reality and find future directions. We cannot overcome crises independently from one another and collaboration is needed, more than ever.

In this context, international collaboration between academia and corporates – the core business of ABIS – The Academy of Business in Society – has a crucial role to play. ABIS will increase our **efforts to be your catalyst of academic-corporate collaborative action** and **social innovations** to address challenges like carbon neutrality, circular economy, equality and social justice.

The awareness of the need for change is increasing. What is still a problem is to focus on what to change; not to fight symptoms, but to solve the underlying causes. It does not really make sense to solve the symptoms of the carbon footprint of an industry if there is no **change of the business model**. There is a pressing need to move away from an efficiency and cost-driven business model **to a sustainable value driven model**. During the [ABIS Colloquium “Business principles for the stakeholder capitalism era”](#) in November 2022, professor Edward Freeman shared his insights how companies can rethink their business models and be successful in **creating both financial and social value**.

Such insights spark many practical “how” questions. How to get where we need to get? How to meet stakeholder interests seemingly at odds? How to transition to more responsible production models? How to implement systemic changes? Getting to new and desired situations, requires first to change the way that we think about an old situation or context: what is needed is a paradigm shift.

It is with pride that we present the highlights of how ABIS contributed to such shift in 2022 via our activities and member engagements. This year we continued our work on **circular economy, sustainable finance** as well as **responsible management education**. At the same time, we incorporated **futures thinking and foresight** into our activities and got engaged with **open science** and **researchers empowerment**. You will notice that we also decided to reorganize our activities into **four new engagement areas**, which you can find more about below.

We count this year again on fruitful academic-corporate collaboration with various stakeholders to make progress in exploring the underlying causes and the “how” questions actively. You can trust our efforts in **creating and disseminating knowledge via publications and research projects**, in **organizing inspiring events** and **opinion leadership activities**, and **fostering the professional and institutional development** of our members through our **foresight tools and workshops**, our **mentoring programme** and the **ABIS sustainability assessment**. These are ways in which we contribute to society and how we are proud to serve our members and partners.

Kindest Regards,

Dr. Ivo Matser EMP
Chief Executive Officer

Prof. Baback Yazdani
Chair of the Board of Directors

About ABIS

ABIS was founded in 2001 and launched at INSEAD in 2002 with the support of the leading business schools in Europe (Ashridge, Bocconi, Copenhagen, Cranfield, ESADE, IESE, IMD, INSEAD, London, Vlerick, Warwick) in partnership with IBM, Microsoft, Johnson & Johnson, Unilever and Shell. The initiative was driven by a shared belief that the challenges linked to globalization and **sustainable development required new management skills, mindsets and capabilities.**

Our network

As one of the few existing business-academic networks, we nurture a unique experience and contribution to a more sustainable world. We trust that research and business have a role to play and we support and cross-pollinate joint efforts between academia and business. Our network is big enough to always have new knowledge and ideas flowing, but also small enough to build strong and unusual bonds and create intimate spaces for brave discussions.

ABIS developed a strong role in responding to this need and it focused on **integrating sustainability at the heart of business curricula, corporate policies and strategies** by providing knowledge and capacity building. Some of our members have been part of our network since our foundation, which is as exciting as welcoming new members, learning and growing together into more responsible and committed individuals and organizations.

We care about our network priorities and needs. We encourage our members to openly share their progress, challenges and dilemmas to learn and further improve. This creates an inclusive community and environment where individuals feel safe to share and value each other's insights and experiences. This contributes to develop and scale up their sustainability efforts in research, education and responsible ways of doing business.

Our 4 Engagement Areas

In 2022, in line with ongoing developments, we updated and restructured our Membership Value and Engagement Opportunities, into the four engagement areas below. Our activities and highlights are summarised within these areas in the pages that follow.

We create resources and facilitate access to relevant insights and research and share best practices to develop sustainability change agency & leadership. We support our members and engage in EU projects on a variety of focused and interdisciplinary issues to drive sustainable development, innovation and change.

Our ambition is to make a significant contribution to the debate and the practice involved in equipping current and future business leaders with the knowledge, skills and capabilities for the long-term success of business in society. We create spaces and discussion platforms fostering thought leadership through our flagship or tailored events.

We empower and foster individual development, change agency and shared learning by providing access to business and academic experts, using effective tools and methodologies and creating supportive connections necessary to contribute to address environmental and social challenges.

We engage institutions by using long-term systemic thinking and management models designed for making continuous improvements, institutional strategy developments and stimulating innovations. We help to increase the outreach and visibility of our members' activities and results.

Knowledge Productivity

- ABIS Special Issues
- Position papers and reports
- EU Research and Innovation projects

Best Sustainability Teaching Practices

ABIS Special Issue

At the **19th Annual Colloquium “Coming full circle? Sustainability and future-proof global recovery”**, business schools scholars and educators presented innovative sustainability teaching practices across three tracks: Sustainability Programmes, Creative Teaching Practices, Business Cases and Industry Engagement.

Some of these were submitted for the **Special Issue “Best Sustainability Teaching Practices”** and embarked with our help on this publishing journey. The Special Issue was published with **8 papers** and a **guest editorial** in the **Emerald Journal of International Education in Business**. This special issue is designed to help the ABIS business-academic network and beyond to gain and access relevant insights to accelerate sustainability uptake, learning capacity and improve the development of sustainable business education. Our hope is that business schools take leadership toward sustainability transitions.

[The guest editorial can be read here](#) (Open Access)

[The Special Issue can be viewed here.](#)

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Driving impact through responsible investing

ABIS Special Issue

In light of ABIS ongoing initiatives concerning this topic, such as the **NN Investment Partners Responsible Investing Summer Course 2021 and 2022**, ABIS convened the **20th Annual Colloquium** highlighting the theme **“Driving impact through responsible investing”** on 23rd November 2021. The conference welcomed responsible investing professionals, business practitioners, as well as scholars and educators in business, management and sustainable finance and engaged them in high level and practice-based dialogues on how to enhance positive business impact on society through responsible investing. The conference offered various views on sustainable investing, as well as corporate perspectives, reflection on the role of business schools and the effect of integrating responsible investing in management education and also latest research findings from academics and practitioners in two tracks:

- ESG, Corporate Governance and Value Creation;
- Responsible Investing approaches and performance.

Following Colloquium, a collaboration was formed with the **Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal (SAMPJ)** to create a Special Issue (SI) with the focus on “Driving impact through responsible investing”, opened to a variety of researchers and practitioners to submit their papers related to the topic.

Academic evidence in the area of responsible investing is increasing, yet its dissemination and impact on real-world investing practices remains fairly limited. With this Special Issue in the SAMPJ, we therefore aim to **strengthen the dialogue between practitioners and academics** about theoretical and practical challenges on:

- how to enhance positive business impact on society through responsible investing
- the alignment among business and investors on investing in sustainable activities

The Special Issue will be published in the second half of 2023.

Our guest editors:

- Joan Fontrodona, Professor and Director of the Business Ethics Department, IESE Business School
- Luk Van Wassenhove, Emeritus Professor of Technology and Operations Management, INSEAD
- Ivo Matser, CEO, ABIS

Transforming business education for sustainability: the case for paradigm shifts in pedagogy and theory

ABIS Position Paper

Delving deeper into "**Futures of Business Education**" for the [Knowledge Into Action Forum](#) in May 2022, the ABIS team and the guest editors of the Special Issue on "**Best Sustainability Teaching Practices**" reflected on **how business schools need to take responsibility for the mindsets, frameworks and management theories they teach and to transform their practices, curricula and research**. These insights and reflections were summarized in a position paper, which has been downloaded hundreds of times and received very encouraging reviews and support by our readers.

It is well known that **businesses across sectors bear responsibility** for the dire state of our environmental ecosystems, be it via resource extraction, energy usage, pollution, but also by luring, if not trapping consumers into a seemingly appealing consumer-oriented lifestyle. Unless **mediated by national political agendas, profit-maximisation and economic growth-oriented paradigms favour the wealthy** at the expense of the less privileged, leading further to social and economic inequality.

The responsibility of business schools lies in taking ownership of the mindset, assumptions, frameworks and theories taught to future and current leaders, studying across the world's business schools. The question is – are business schools ready for not only participating in the education of future leaders, but further, for taking leadership of the global transformation needed to secure the sustainable future of the planet? Addressing grand challenges calls for **recognizing the role of business schools** creating and maintaining the vicious circle of environmental degradation coupled with social and economic inequality.

The awareness of the need for change is widespread, but **the shift from profit maximisation to the betterment of society is still not reflected in many business education textbooks and pedagogies**, as well as in the dominant management and economic theories. Faced with ecological and potential societal collapse, business schools need to do more.

In this position paper, the authors focus on and summarize important bodies of literature **calling for the creation of sustainable mindsets** and **advocate for both pedagogical transformation** and a **reconsideration of the theoretical underpinnings in business education**. The hope is for business schools to **take true leadership toward sustainability transitions**.

The position paper is divided into sections:

- Background
- Overview
- Literatures informing a Sustainability 3.0 mindset
- From pedagogical innovation to transformation...or revolution?!
- Management theory: from hindrance to catalyst of sustainability transformations?
- Bibliography

Access the [Position paper here](#).

Exploring the Enablers of CE Practices: The case of businesses and business schools

ABIS Research Report

In March 2021, we published a report “**Exploring the Enablers of Circular Economy Practices: The case of businesses and business schools**”.

The report investigates **what motivates decision-makers to adopt circular practices** within the context of businesses, business networks and business schools. The research behind this report **aims to provide new insights to understand how circular practices are adopted** and **how this transition can be further boosted** from the perspective of businesses and business schools.

The research is based on a **set of 20 interviews** to key stakeholders who are involved in the adoption and development of Circular Economy strategies of businesses, or of research groups and teaching programs within business schools.

The CE adoption can be primarily motivated by **two enablers**:

- The realignment of pre-existing sustainable or social responsibility practices with CE practices;
- The explicit action of a decision-maker within a business or a business school, such as a CEO or a dean.

This report also identifies four factors that encourage decisionmakers to adopt the CE:

- The need to adapt to global challenges;
- The influence of business networks;
- The influence of the market and social dynamics;
- Governmental pressure.

All identified drivers affect both businesses and business schools. However, most of the drivers that push for the adoption of CE **originate from a bottom-up perspective**, and factors as the governmental pressure play a low profile when shaping CE practices.

This may lead to an inconsistent adoption of CE, as there is no unified **approach to define and evaluate the emergence of CE practices**, potentially leading to a weak version of the CE with low environmental benefits. At the same time, it opens up **specific opportunities for business schools and governments to step up their leadership** in the CE transformation needed to secure a sustainable future.

The report is structured as follows:

- Existing literature on the drivers for the adoption of CE practices
- Methods and data used to build this research
- Results are presented and discussed in comparison to the existing research
- Conclusions
- Opportunities for business schools
- Key takeaways

The lead author of the report is our colleague Josep Pinyol, Early Stage Researcher for the ReTraCE project and a PhD candidate at the University of Exeter, supported by the ABIS team.

[Full access to the research report.](#)

Realizing the Transition Towards a Circular Economy (ReTraCE)

EU Research and Innovation projects

Since 2018, ABIS was part of a consortium led by **University of Sheffield** in **EU Horizon 2020 project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)** called "**ReTrace**" - **Realizing the Transition to the Circular Economy**. The consortium is composed of *University of Sheffield, Università Degli Studi di Napoli Parthenope, Universitaet Kassel, SEERC, ABIS, Hogskolan Dalarna, University of Kent, TATA Steel UK, Olympia Electronics and Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam*. The partners also include *University of Exeter, Leeds University Business School, University of Ulsan and Shanghai Jiao Tong University*.

The main aim of the ReTraCE project was to create **a cohort of professionals capable of driving the transition towards the Circular Economy** and employable not only by research institutions, but also by public sector bodies (e.g. local authorities and national agencies) and manufacturing and service sectors including: metals industry, electric and electronic equipment manufacturing, construction materials and waste management. The consortium delivers world class multidisciplinary training to **15 Early Stage Researchers (ESRs)** offering them an extended and valuable program of international exchanges and secondments through the wide network of partner organisations from public, private and third sectors.

One of these 15 researchers is **Josep Pinyol**, who was hosted by ABIS since May 2019. He is also enrolled in the PhD programme in Sustainable Futures at the *University of Exeter Business School*.

We organized Two successful **project meetings with industry and policy experts** online and in Brussels in May 2020 and December 2021, with the aim to **support the professional development** of the ESRs while gaining practical information from experts working in the field.

In 2022 we organized **two Scenario Exploration System** workshops which were designed to explore two **potential pathways for a Circular Economy by 2050** during the **Final ReTraCE event** held in **Thessaloniki**. The workshops were delivered to around **15 Early Stage Researchers** from the ReTraCE consortium, together with their supervisors and other consortium partners. The second workshop was held with the collaboration of another project **JUST2CE** and **local stakeholders** were invited to participate in order to discuss practically how the **region of North Macedonia can embark on the circular transition**.

The project is officially ending in 2023, with the last final conference taking place in Brussels in March 2023 where **policy briefs and recommendations for a Circular Economy transition** will be presented.

Open and Universal Science (OPUS)

EU Research and Innovation projects

The project **OPUS: Open and Universal Science** under the **Horizon Europe** programme, HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01 call, with the duration of 36 months, officially started off with a kick-off meeting in September 2022 in Gran Canaria, the headquarters of the coordinator partner PLOCAN.

The project aims to **reform the assessment of research and researchers** towards a system that incentivises and rewards them to practice **Open Science**. The consortium led by *PLOCAN* has **18 academic and non-academic partners**. ABIS will support the project aim in **developing a set of interventions to implement Open Science**, as well as **metrics** to monitor and drive Open Science. We will also engage with our members from **industry** providing with their perspective on the topic and support the **dissemination and communication** of the project outcomes.

OPUS uses the term 'Open Science' to refer to practices providing **open access to research outputs, early and open sharing of research**, participation in **open peer-review**, measures to ensure **reproducibility of results**, and **involving citizens, civil society, and end-users** in the **co-creation of research and innovation** agendas and content.

With this interpretation of Open Science, OPUS will deliver a state of the art of existing literature for Open Science, **interventions to implement a reformed Open Science system** at Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs). OPUS will **develop indicators and metrics to monitor the implementation of the interventions**. In particular, **incentives to reward researchers** to practise Open Science will be developed and tested.

In particular, OPUS will **test interventions and indicators and metrics** for Open Science via **3 pilot RPOs** (Nova University Lisbon, University of Rijeka, and University of Cyprus) and **2 pilot RFOs** from Lithuania and Romania (RCL and UEFISCDI). These pilot organisations will learn from both each other and draw experience from external experts in **mutual learning exercises**. The results of the pilots will be translated into **policy briefs** and thematic workshops that will help to raise awareness, build trust, and drive the uptake of Open Science in the community.

Following the kick-off meeting, ABIS was involved in Work Package 1 to deliver a **literature review on industry practices in Open Science and Open Innovation**.

The consortium met again in February 2023 in Brussels to discuss together with the pilot organisations on their **existing relevant activities** as well as to start discussing the **comprehensive list of interventions and indicators, metrics, structure and monitoring of the Action Plans** for the pilot organisations.

In order to maximise the relevance and benefits of the framework of indicators and metrics, we are also **gathering inputs from our business-academic network on the existing or planned practices and policies for Open Science**.

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE)

EU Research and Innovation projects

The **Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE)** project, granted by the EU under the Horizon Europe programme for the duration of 2 years, has kicked-off its mission at the coordinating institution **PLOCAN** headquarters in Gran Canaria in January 2023 with all 18 partner organisations across Europe.

The aim of the project is to develop coordination and support measures to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common **Research Career Framework (RCF)** and **Tenure Track-like Models (TTL)** that offers a suite of options to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers with **the aim of improving research careers and reducing career precarity**.

The RCF will recognise the research profession across sectors, provide a **career development and progression structure for research careers**, recognise both research and transferable skills and competences, facilitate **intersectoral collaboration and mobility**, and offer **solutions to the precariousness of research careers** in academia. SECURE will test aspects of the RCF and TTL models in trials in four Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), one Research Funding Organisation (RFO), and one recruitment agency.

The ABIS role will be to bring in the **industry perspective, involving business communities**, understanding and improving the **intersectoral mobility** and **promoting the models to business** in order to **strengthen the interaction with business for access to labour market**. We will also use all the **project outcomes to disseminate and exploit with our academic members**.

Exploring Plausible Circular Futures (ExPliCit)

EU Research and Innovation projects

We have also started a 3 year project on **“Exploring Plausible Circular Futures” (ExPliCit)**, funded by the EU under the Horizon Europe programme, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Staff Exchanges.

Circular Economy (CE) represents a new paradigm that is capable of pushing the frontiers of sustainable development by transforming the relationships between ecological systems and economic activities. Such a new paradigm is expected to repair economy-society-nature interactions, replacing the current linear economic model with a new one that is restorative and regenerative by intention and design. However, while there is a common agreement that the transition towards a CE could foster more sustainable futures, there is a **lack of discussion about how a truly circular economic system should be organised**. Most of the current literature on CE fails to recognise this, **presenting the transition towards a CE as a straightforward, neutral, and apolitical process**, implicitly characterised by a techno-optimistic and eco-modernist stance.

Within this context, **this project calls for opening up a debate to deconstruct the increasingly hegemonic discourse of Circular Economy** based on a technocratic approach and reconstruct it by embedding normative and political dimensions, looking at a **plurality of plausible CE futures**, and discussing their **implications in terms of the organisation of production and distribution networks**, also **involving a wide set of stakeholders**. As such, the project will involve a plurality of disciplinary perspectives, in order to devise future supply chain configurations that could be implemented in specific industrial sectors under specific CE scenarios.

A wide array of non-academic beneficiaries ensures that the project will be capable of **realising and sharing relevant knowledge transfer through secondment mechanisms**.

The project includes **10 partners**:

- The coordinator: *Università Degli Studi di Napoli Parthenope*
- Academic partners: *University of Vigo, Università Degli Studi di Catania, University of Sevilla, University of Scheffield*
- Non-academic partners: *CNA Campania Nord, Federco, AAEL, Revertia and ABIS*

The kick-off meeting took place at Università Degli Studi di Napoli Parthenope, in Naples on January 2023 and served to start organizing the related tasks and plan secondment action plans.

The role of ABIS will be to share our experiences and **knowledge with foresight methods** and **tailor the Scenario Exploration System for Circular Economy scenarios**, with focus on supply chains. ABIS will organize **three specialized SES workshops in Pontevedra, Brussels and Sheffield**.

ABIS will start sending as well as receiving secondees from March 2023.

Events & Opinion Leadership

- ABIS events
- Opinion Leadership

Knowledge Into Action Forum

"Futures of Business Education"

On May 10-11, 2022 we organized the ABIS 8th Knowledge Into Action Forum during which speakers and participants engaged in keynote speeches, panel discussions and interactive sessions on the timely topic of "**Futures of Business Education**". The event took place online on May 10 and in person in Brussels on May 11.

True to its mission, ABIS believes that more than ever **business schools need to take responsibility for the mindsets, frameworks and management theories they teach** and to **transform their practices, curricula and research** as laid out into our recent [position paper](#).

Building on the growing foresight knowledge and competences ABIS has been developing, we approached this topic through the lens of **futures studies, foresight and anticipatory governance**. The aim was to offer original, novel insights and solutions to foster **pedagogical innovation, interdisciplinary and epistemic dialogue** around **management theory** as well as **institutional transformation** in business education.

Njeri Mwagiru, Senior Futurist at the **Institute for Futures Research, Stellenbosch Business School** gave an insightful opening speech addressing the relevance of future studies, addressing the main critique: current curricula perpetuating problematic paradigms from the industrialization era. She called for the need to identify new trajectory for business, business schools and society in the 21st century.

Following a panel discussion on "**Transforming business education for sustainable futures**" welcoming high-level voices from policymakers, academia and business to share recent development and emerging pathways to uplevel the role of business school to ensure sustainable futures. The moderator set forth key undertakings by the European Commission on the changes in education needed to support the EU goals within the EU Green Deal, such as the European Skills Agenda and the most recent Learning for environmental sustainability proposal

The two following sessions zoomed into a specific theme which is going to have a great impact on the future of business education, and its ability to address pressing societal challenges: **pedagogy and skills development**.

- **Applying the European competence framework on sustainability** with **Ulrike Pisiotis**, Policy Officer, DG Education, **European Commission**
- **Taking climate leadership: preparing students for challenging times** with **Petra Molthan-Hill**, Professor, **Nottingham Business School**

The final session of Day 1 harvested the learnings from the morning and the interactive sessions and reflected on how they influence the future institutional developments of business schools through participating to a fishbowl discussion.

During the second day participants engaged in an **active and dynamic exploration of futures of business education** via **facilitated foresight tools and methods**. The objective was to **explore the driving forces and underlying factors** that are going to **shape how business education is going to look like** in the decades to come. These insights are going to inform an **emerging initiative** for the ABIS network aimed to accelerate the needed changes in business schools via the **identification of four pathways to alternative future scenarios of business education**.

21st ABIS Annual Colloquium

"Business principles for the stakeholder capitalism era"

ABIS convened its 21st Annual Colloquium during which speakers and participants engaged on the timely topic of "**Business principles for the stakeholder capitalism era**". The event took place online on November 29 and in hybrid format on November 30.

Academics, progressive businesses and international organizations like ABIS have been calling for an "expanded" role of business in society for decades (most recently at the Value Creation Roundtables co-organized by ABIS).

In this Colloquium, we aimed to move beyond specificities and fragmented approaches towards a **holistic understanding of responsible business conduct** in light of the evolving concept of **stakeholder capitalism**. Albeit not new, this concept has been reforming the way we think about business and advocating for a system in which businesses are oriented to serve the interests of all their stakeholders. The main outcome of the event was a **set of principles** serving as guideposts for business in the stakeholder capitalism era.

The Colloquium welcomed **managers, practitioners** and **business and management scholars** who want to **enhance business competitiveness** as well as **social** and **environmental sustainability** in a world in transition **towards more inclusive, stakeholder and regenerative models**.

The official program started with a panel discussion "**Managing Business in the Stakeholder Capitalism Era**" that welcomed relevant voices from **ABB Group, Social Value UK** and **George Mason University**. Our panelists **Luca Condosta, Crispin Sachikonye** and **Lisa Gring-Pemble** presented their academic and corporate perspectives on the theory and practice of stakeholder capitalism and its implications for sustainability strategy, business model innovation and management.

Research and case presentations followed, with six different tracks, where academic experts and practitioners from the ABIS network and beyond presented their **latest research findings and cases** at the **crossroads of sustainability strategy, business model innovation** and **stakeholder capitalism**.

The second day featured two keynotes - corporate and academic. **Pauline Bieringa** from **Triodos Bank** pointed out the **paradigm shift towards community** as the center of **purpose-based corporate action** and the need to move beyond net-zero to transformation and regeneration. The academic keynote by Professor Edward Freeman "**The power of AND - Implementing stakeholder capitalism**" focused on what it takes to run a business successfully in today's world, specifically how **business models have to change**. He proposed five main ideas and principles to **drive responsible business conduct**.

In the last session, our participants engaged in an interactive discussion reflecting on the **key takeaways, trends** and **emerging responsibilities** for corporate action. The main outcome was a preliminary set of principles that could serve as guideposts for business in the stakeholder capitalism era.

The principles and main insights from the event are summarized in [the event report](#).

NN IP Responsible Investing Summer Course

For the third consecutive year we had the pleasure to collaborate with **NN Investment Partners** to organise the **NN IP Responsible Investing Summer Course - 2022 edition** that took place both online and in-person from 24 August until October 5.

This lecture series builds on the success of the Responsible Investing Summer Course 2021 with high-profile academics offering valuable insights for professional investors. This time the summer course focused on **Sustainable Investing: The Just Transition** and offered informed and in-depth viewpoints on topics such as:

- The implications of recent **governance frameworks** (the **EU taxonomy** and other regional legislations)
- The anticipated risks and case studies of mitigation efforts against them
- **Ethical investing**: How do we come to a decision when there are conflicting priorities in our investments

The purpose of the Summer Course was to provide the NN IP professional investors and stakeholders with the latest academic thinking about sustainability. This time, the format offered **7 hybrid, interactive, thought-provoking lectures** from **leading academics** all around the globe. True to our mission, we were able to **bridge the academic and corporate world**. Leading academics from our network organizations and beyond including *Maastricht University, ESMT Berlin, Bocconi University, University of Singapore, London School of Economics, Vrije Universiteit Brussel* and *University of Virginia* gave in-depth presentations on their expertise and experience about **the implications in the short and long-term investment outlook**.

At ABIS, we were very happy to contribute to:

- Assessing potential speakers for Summer Course
- Coordinating all communication, admin and finance between speakers and NN IP
- Knowledge support during briefing process and at Q&As
- Content management for NN IP marketing collaterals and its coordination with speakers

	24 August, Singapore Prof. Sumit Agarwal at the National University of Singapore The intersection of behavioural finance and sustainability and green finance
	30 August, Utrecht Prof. Dr. Nancy Bocken at the Maastricht University Towards sustainable circular businesses - challenges and opportunities
	5 September, Berlin President and Prof. Jörg Rocholl at ESMT Berlin Green finance: How investors can make companies go green
	14 September, London Dr. Erica Thompson at the London School of Economics Understanding the limitations of mathematical modelling for sustainable transitions and risk management
	20 September, Brussels Prof. Dr. Cathy Macharis at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel With a factor 8 to the mobility system of the future
	27 September, Virginia Prof. R. Edward Freeman at the University of Virginia The Power of AND: Implementing Stakeholder Capitalism
	5 October, Milan Assoc. Prof. Hannes F. Wagner at the Bocconi University Renewable Governance: Good for the Environment?

Professional Development

- Mentoring programme
- Scenario Exploration System

ABIS Mentoring Programme

Mentoring Programme for Early Stage Researchers

In line with our mission, the **ABIS Mentoring Programme** aims to **strengthen the learning and development** for **Early Stage Researchers (ESRs)** and **creating supportive connections** that are necessary in order to contribute to address today's environmental and social challenges.

Many ESRs today seek to find their ways developing their careers while also contributing to **make a positive impact**. At ABIS, we have hosted many young and talented researchers at events and conferences, and having been involved in many MSCA International Training Networks, we perceive how **in need ESRs are of both personal and professional support** to flourish in their careers and **take part in the sustainability transformation**.

After a successful Mentoring programme pilot that run from October 2021 until June 2022, we continued the programme again in September 2022 with new mentor and mentee cohort.

The core of the programme is a set of **6-8 hours of 1:1 mentoring sessions** from our **highly experienced mentors** over **9 months**, helping ESRs progress in their careers and make an impact on society. The programme also includes **regular workshops** and **online calls** organized by ABIS. The whole programme lasts **9 months**.

The interest among our network was very high as we received nearly **30 mentor and mentee applications**, from which through a couple of **matchmaking events**, we were able to put together **6 couples** that signed **mentoring agreements**. After an introductory **kick-off event** where we laid down the program structure, timeline, fundamental mentoring rules and the participants' expectations, we also scheduled **2 workshops** aiming for further ESRs' professional development and growth. The sessions included:

- Researchers as changemakers - research impact vs academic rigour
- Responsible Research for business and management

Throughout the whole process informal sessions with mentors and mentees are organized to gain feedback and insights about this programme.

We are pleased to work with our mentoring couples and finish off with a celebration event on 22 June 2023.

Calls for mentors and mentees for upcoming Mentoring programme will be communicated by summer 2023. The expected beginning of the **next Mentoring programme is September 2023**.

[Read more about the Mentoring Programme.](#)

ABIS
The Academy of Business in Society

**Mentoring Programme for ESRs
in sustainability**

Kick-off event

25 October 2022

Karolina Sobczak - Knowledge Manager, ABIS

Scenario Exploration System

The **Scenario Exploration System (SES)** is a **serious foresight and gaming tool** developed by the **European Commission's Joint Research Centre** to facilitate the practical use of scenarios from **foresight** studies, engage participants in **systemic long-term thinking** while exploring **alternative sustainable futures** in the role of different societal stakeholders.

SES Taster Sessions

In order to share the tool with our network and beyond, we have introduced **monthly one-hour Taster Sessions**. In this session we give a quick **overview of the tool** and **showcase a practical and interactive example** of how to play digitally. The participants gain a better understanding about the key **benefits, learnings** and the **dynamics** of the tool. In 2022 we have organized **7 Taster Sessions** with over **70 participants** and this number is increasing every month.

[To join us for a Taster Session click here and register.](#)

SES Digital and Physical version

To be able to play the game easily with anybody around the world, we developed a **digital version** of the tool. During several sessions, we understood that the quality of the workshop remains extremely high even in digital format, the participants gained many insights and learnings from it. The digital version among others has the advantage that it can be played with different stakeholders all around the world.

However, after the pandemic, we see growing interest in organizing the Scenario Exploration System in person and we must agree that we enjoy it slightly more in person as the interactions and the game dynamics are slightly richer!

[Read more about the Scenario Exploration System.](#)

SES tailored workshops and trainings

The SES workshop has been increasingly popular. We take great care when organizing a SES workshop as the tool is **highly versatile** and can be **tailored to every client need** and every scenario or topic. The SES can be used in academic context as a teaching tool but also for strategic aims for internal management teams both in business and academia.

Throughout 2022 we delivered **6 tailored workshops** for both members and non-members and public bodies.

1. SES JRC Bioeconomy:

We are proud to have supported the organization and tailoring of a new SES version exploring bioeconomy foresight scenarios (**Bioeconomy 2050**) for the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. Based on that, we facilitated **2 workshops** in October and December 2022 held in Brussels to engage more than **60 key European stakeholders** in the bioeconomy field (primary producers, business representatives, policy makers, consumers and youth ambassadors) in reflections and discussions about how the future of bioeconomy can be shaped towards the direction we want.

2. ReTraCE Circular Economy scenarios

We facilitated two Scenario Exploration System workshops tailored to explore two **potential pathways for a Circular Economy** during the **Final ReTraCE event in June 2022, Thessaloniki, Greece**. The workshops were delivered to around **15 Early Stage Researchers** from the ReTraCE consortium, together with their supervisors and other consortium partners. The second workshop was held with the collaboration of another EU project **JUST2CE** and **local stakeholders from policy and business** were invited to participate in order to discuss practically how the region of North Macedonia can embark on the circular transition.

3. JEE Europe

As every year, we took in the biggest **JEE Europe annual conference** and deliver a workshop for more than 35 young entrepreneurs, offering insights into **futures literacy, systemic thinking**, the role of different stakeholders and the **importance of collaboration** while exploring the plausible **Sustainable Lifestyles in 2050**.

4. Kozminski University

We were pleased to offer a one-time facilitation workshop to our long-term member Kozminski University and their **leadership team** and the **academic heads of departments** and professors.

Institutional Development

- Scenario Exploration System -
Facilitator Training
- ABIS Sustainability Assessment

Scenario Exploration System - Training

A serious foresight and gaming tool

SES Facilitator Training

On top of one-off Scenario Exploration System workshops, we also offer **trainings for future facilitators** (game masters) of the tool. We have trained around **60 facilitators** from *Stellenbosch Institute for Sustainable Futures*, *Liverpool John Moores University*, *SCO Sweden*, *JE Europe*, *Liverpool John Moores Business School* and *Manchester Metropolitan University*.

- We have trained the professors as well as students two years in a row from **Liverpool John Moores University**. They have integrated the SES tool as a core part of their **undergraduate programme on International Business Management** and its **CSR module** for **100 students**. The students themselves volunteered for extra responsibility and acted as game facilitators for their other classmates.
- Around 20 staff members from different departments of **Manchester Metropolitan University** received an in-person full-day training in Manchester in September 2022 and they are currently preparing to use the serious gaming and foresight tool within a number of programmes at different academic level.

Our members and clients choose this option if they know they would like to integrate this tool on a **large scale** (such as offering it to more than 50 students) and are thinking of repeating it or **integrating it in a module for several years**.

The Facilitator Training consists of:

- Playing the game to get a hands-on experience of the tool (2.5 - 3 hours)
- Lecture with practical examples/ cases and Q&A (2,5 hours)
- Access to all materials for further learnings, digitalized SES version, SES Sustainable Lifestyles 2050 version for printing, Game Facilitator guides and everything needed to be fully prepared for a facilitation

Sustainability Assessment

A management model designed by ABIS

In 2021 ABIS developed its **Sustainability Assessment**, a **management model** designed to **integrate sustainability in higher education institutions**. Its purpose is to report to decision-makers of these institutions about the actual status of **sustainability implementation at institutional and academic level** and to engage them in **continuous improvement**. The assessment analyses and informs which enablers are leading to sustainable transformation as well as how it is perceived by relevant stakeholders and provides with **recommendations** for effective further developments.

The assessment consists of

- **a survey** of 60 questions containing different sub-sets directed to *key internal and external stakeholders* focusing on *sustainability enablers and performances*
- **a report** from the analysis of the processed answers from the survey

The report can be presented at the internal executive decision making meetings or it can be used as part of the self-assessment report for the institution's national or international accreditation purposes. The ABIS Sustainability Assessment report will provide **context and evidence** of the **institution's sustainability initiatives and performance**.

ABIS has piloted the assessment with **ESMT Berlin** and **Nottingham Business School in 2022**. The outcomes of the report are confidential, but we are working on providing you with testimonials from the HEIs that took part in the assessment.

We are also organizing **Info Sessions** on a bi-monthly basis and would be pleased to explain it more in detail. Please register here.

You can also take a look at the [ABIS Sustainability Assessment Guide](#).

Other ABIS News

New Board of Directors 2022 - 2025

During the **ABIS General Assembly** that took place on July 6th 2022, the **new Board of Directors was approved**. The proposed composition was based on **diversity criteria** as **gender, geography, ethnicity** and **culture** as well as decision-making position. Considering all criteria, the General Assembly approved the proposed Board of Directors unanimously. The members of the ABIS Board of Directors for the term 2022-2025 are:

- **Baback Yazdani**, Professor and Executive Dean, **Nottingham Business School** (Chair of the Board)
- **Manuela Brusoni**, Associate Professor and Director of Quality Accreditation and Benchmarking, **SDA Bocconi**
- **Joan Fontrodona**, Professor and Director, Business Ethics Department, **IESE**
- **Chris Fuggle**, Global Head of Sustainability, **Mazars**
- **Marian Garcia**, Professor and Dean, **Kent Business School**
- **Lisa Gring-Pemble**, Associate Professor and Executive Director, Business for a Better World Center, **George Mason University**
- **Adrie Heinsbroek**, Chief Sustainability Officer, **NN Investment Partners**
- **Joanna Radeke**, Executive Director, FUTURE Institute for Sustainable Transformation, **ESMT Berlin**
- **Boleslaw Rok**, Professor and Director, Positive Entrepreneurship Research Lab, **Kozminski University**
- **Kosheek Sewchurran**, Associate Professor and Director of Executive MBA, **Graduate School of Business, Cape Town** (*co-opted*)

New Membership Value and Engagement Opportunities report

We released an updated version of the **Membership Value and Engagement Opportunities report**, the **four engagement areas** in which we operate: **Knowledge Productivity, Events & Opinion Leadership, Professional Development, Institutional Development**.

In the report we are providing more clarity to all the activities and initiatives that are available to all of our members and/or clients.

The **Membership Value and Engagement Opportunities report** can be accessed [here](#).

For even more detailed information, please refer to our annual **Highlight Reports** where we describe our network's involvement in each of the engagement areas.

JE Europe Winter Conference 2022

For the fourth year in a row we took an active part at the **Junior Enterprises Europe (JE Europe) Winter Conference**, a flagship annual event for around 400 junior entrepreneurs and young leaders that took place on March 3-5. Our CEO Ivo Matser delivered a **keynote speech** at the opening ceremony. The ABIS team hosted a **Scenario Exploration System Workshop online** for over 35 junior entrepreneurs, where they engaged with foresight scenarios and took on different societal roles that contribute to achieving a more sustainable future. Moreover, we took part in a jury and awarded the **Best Sustainable Junior Enterprise**.

LJMU Social Value at Universities, Global Symposia

We were honoured to support **Liverpool John Moores University, Business School** in the organization and dissemination of their **Social Value at Universities, Global Symposia** in July 2022. The two day hybrid event aimed at exploring and maximising the Social Value potential of universities and business schools.

ABIS Team and Board

ABIS Team

Ivo Matser
Chief Executive Officer

Karolina Sobczak
Knowledge Manager

Katarina Haluskova
Project Communication Specialist

Giulia Lizzi
Business Development & Membership Officer

Josep Pinyol
Early Stage Researcher
Circular Economy

Antonino Mangano
Office Manager & Communication Support

ABIS Board of Directors

Baback Yazdani
Chair of the Board of Directors &
Dean of Nottingham Business
School

Manuela Brusoni
Associate Professor
SDA Bocconi School of
Management

Marian Garcia
Professor and Dean
Kent Business School

Joan Fontrodona
Full Professor
IESE Business School

Adrie Heinsbroek
Chief Sustainability Officer
NN Investment Partners

Chris Fuggle
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Mazars

Joanna Radeke
Executive Director of the Futurist
Institute for Sustainable Transformation
ESMT Berlin

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